

A STUDY OF DIPLOMATIC ARABIC TRANSLATION

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Annotatsiya: *Bugungi kunda diplomatiya va diplomatik jarayonlar butun dunyo bo'ylab misli ko'rilmagan yangi bir bosqichga chiqmoqda. Diplomatiya xalqaro aloqalar va diplomatik pozitsiyalar, turli xil milliy masalalar va manfaatlarni o'z ichiga oladigan sohadir. Yuqoridagi jarayonlarning barchasi esa o'z navbatida diplomat tarjimonlarga talabning yuqoriligi va diplomatik tarjimaning aktuallik darajasini oshishiga olib kelmoqda. Diplomatik tarjimaning umumiy tarjima bilan mos keluvchi xususiyatlari ham bor bo'lib: tarjima ishi original matnga rioya qilishi va uni aniq hamda to'g'ri yetkazilishi kabilarni misol keltirish mumkin. Diplomatik tilning xususiyatlarini tushunish diplomatik tarjima texnikalari va strategiyalarini o'rganishga yordam beradi. Quyidagi maqolada diplomatik tarjima, tarjimon madaniyati va moslashtirish nazariyalariga doir masalalar ko'rib chiqiladi.*

Аннотация: *Сегодня дипломатия и дипломатические процессы вступают в новую фазу на мировом уровне. Дипломатия охватывает международные отношения и дипломатические позиции, а также различные национальные вопросы и интересы. Все эти факторы, в свою очередь, способствуют росту спроса на дипломатов-переводчиков и увеличению актуальности дипломатического перевода. Дипломатический перевод также имеет общие черты с общим переводом, такими как необходимость точного и правильного соблюдения оригинального текста. Понимание особенностей дипломатического языка помогает в изучении техник и стратегий дипломатического перевода. В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы, связанные с дипломатическим переводом и ролью переводчика в дипломатическом дискурсе.*

Abstract: *Diplomacy encompasses international relations and diplomatic positions, as well as various national issues and interests. All of these factors, in turn, contribute to the increasing demand for diplomatic translators and the growing relevance of diplomatic translation. Diplomatic translation also shares common features with general translation, such as the need to adhere to the original text and convey it accurately and correctly. Understanding the characteristics of diplomatic language helps in studying diplomatic translation techniques and strategies. In this article the focus will be on the issues related to diplomatic translation and the role of the translator in diplomatic discourse.*

Keywords: *Pragmatic Translation, Relevance adaptation theory, Arabic-English translation, Diplomacy, Diplomatic translation.*

Introduction. In the 21st Century Arabic country have become the realm of business development and hotspot places around the world especially in the energy, construction, technology and real estate industries, which have given big economic boosts to many petroleum powerhouse countries like Saudi Arabia or UAE and Qatar that claim Arabic as an official language. The same thing goes for diplomatic, governmental and political careers that address and deal with policy in the Arab world.¹ In international relations diplomacy usually refers to a government's activities, mainly in the form of visits, negotiations, conclusion of treaties, issuance of diplomatic documents, participation in international conferences and international organizations, etc. One of the hot majors discussed in recent years is diplomatic translation. The discussion comes not only from the translation department of the ministry of foreign affairs, but also from universities and research institutions. Diplomatic translation is also a hot topic for students' graduation thesis. Diplomatic translation mainly involves the translation of foreign affairs activities of national leaders, treaties, issues, challenges, diplomatic documents and international conferences. However, these seem to lack dynamic research. One of the major difficulties in cross-cultural communication is that in many cases there are great differences in the quantity and nature of information shared. From the perspective of translatology, in order to solve the above problems and successfully meet the needs of communication, appropriate translation methods should be selected strategically. In recent years, many scholars have discussed pragmatics and translation from the perspectives of presupposition, politeness principle, conversational implicature, relevance theory, speech act theory, conversational analysis, etc., and have achieved certain results.

Relevance-adaptation translation theory. Translation is challenging task of linguistics. It has always been a complicated job, specially transferring the characteristics and properties of two languages belonging to different origins. "Translation is not a matter of words only: it is a matter of making intelligible a whole culture. So, translating Arabic texts into English necessitates a huge bilingual expertise. Moreover, the cultural and religious influences are very strong in both the languages. It has been shown that though lexical problems are greater in number, grammatical, stylistic, usage and phonological problems are not insignificant². The speaker will express his/her utterance information, while the hearer will judge the speaker's utterance information first, and then combine with the information knowledge related to the context stored in his/her brain to exert his/her cognitive ability to obtain the context assumption of the utterance and deduce the speaker's communicative intention. Through cognitive explicitness and pragmatic

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inference, the process of achieving contextual effects with minimal effort in order to achieve optimal relevance. Translation is to reproduce the information in the original text in the most natural way in the recipient language, first reproducing the meaning and then the style. Language has variability, negotiability and adaptability. Variability is a linguistic feature that limits the possible range of choices, i.e. language has a series of selectable possibilities and it develops dynamically. The process of language use is the process of continuous language selection. This language selection process is carried out under the conscious or unconscious state of the language user, and may also be realized due to the internal needs of the language or due to the influence of external factors. It emphasizes the study of the translation process, regards translation as a communicative act that continuously carries out dynamic inference according to the context to achieve mutual understanding, and points out that optimal relevance is the basic principle that restricts translation. That is, language users can make flexible changes from selectable items to meet the needs of communication. Communicative translation attempts to produce an effect as close as possible to the effect of the original text on the target readers, and semantic translation attempts to convey the exact contextual meaning of the original text as closely as possible within the scope permitted by the semantic and syntactic structure of the target language. This theory mainly focuses on how people make language choices in communication and provides an important theoretical basis for translators to choose translation strategies and techniques in translation.

In recent years, some scholars have introduced relevance theory and adaptation theory into translation studies. That is, the success of translation mainly depends on whether the original author, the translator and the reader can achieve the best relevance, in other words, the translator seeks the best relevance from the express communication behavior of the original author in the translation process. It can be seen that semantic translation focuses on the form and semantics of the original text, while communicative translation emphasizes functional equivalence. In order to facilitate communication, the translation can take into account many factors other than words. The context in translation activities can be linguistic context, situational context and cultural context. Language context mainly includes intratextual cohesion and linear sequence. Interpretation process refers to the communication process between the translator and the source language author.

Strict Language in Diplomatic Translation. The translation of diplomatic agreements and documents including inter-state interest relations, territorial issues and cooperation issues, as well as issues related to the country's political, security, economic and military interests, should proceed with caution. Diplomatic translators must carefully consider and accurately convey them. Through this process, the translator will realize the best correlation between his cognitive hypothesis and the communicative intention of the source language. The process of discourse production is the process of the translator's dynamic adaptation to the target readers. According to his own understanding of the original author's communicative intention deduced in the first communication process, as well as the translated language environment and his

expectation of the translated readers, as listeners, should make corresponding inferences. There is no room for careless translation of diplomatic documents. The rigour of diplomatic language requires that the proper balance of diplomatic language must be in place and there must be no mistakes. The translator needs to be guided by the principle of optimal relevance, constantly make adaptive language choices in the process of transmitting the intention of the source language author, and consider whether it is related to the language context, social and cultural context and the translator's psychological motivation of the target language. And spend the least effort to meet the readers' expectation of cognitive effects, the translator will achieve the ultimate goal of translation validity, thus achieving the maximum convergence of validity to the target text and the original text.

Conclusion Diplomatic translation involves the relationship between countries, about the political and national levels. The position of the diplomatic translator should be clear, and a thorough analysis should be made of the policies, various society and cultures of each country and the world. Diplomatic translation should first interpret the original diplomatic intention and search the best connection with the original diplomacy, then make dynamic adaptation and make language choice. Translation has the characteristic of cognitive relevance, and the essence of translation is the process of twice ostensive and inferential under the restriction of cognitive context. However, the process of translation is a process of continuous dynamic selection and adaptation according to language, culture and social background. The study of culture-specific items from the perspective of adaptation theory constructs a theoretical framework for translating culture-specific items and makes active and dynamic adaptation in the process of translation, thus realizing the ultimate goal of language communication in translation.

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